

TREASURE

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Training of Early Stage Researchers: a Pilot Study**

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research (RROR) practices and outputs list,
criteria and procedures
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Contributors: [core team members] Ana Santos Carvalho, Bruno Direito, Catarina Domingues, Elsa Henriques, Fernando V. Borges, Inês A. T. Almeida, João Ramalho-Santos, Jorge Noro, Maria João Neves, Paulo J. Oliveira, Tracey L. Weissgerber, [local advisory board members] Ana M. Teixeira, Carmen Soares, Carolina Cabaços, Cláudia Cavadas, Gonçalo Santos, Henrique Girão, Isabel V. Figueiredo, João Gabriel Silva, João Peça, Jorge Varanda, Liliana Baptista, Luís C. Dias, Luiza Franco, Marco Pereira, Maria Cohen, Maria João Antunes, Maria Manuel Borges, Mariana Linharelhos, Nuno Empadinhas, Paulo Pinheiro, Pedro A. Santos, Sabrina Pereira, Sofia Wasterlain, [external advisory board members] Bruno Béu, Matthew Lucas, Miriam Kip, Natalie C. Evans, Tamarinde Haven, [external stakeholders] Priya Silverstein, Thomas Feliciani
Reviewed and authorized: Vice-rector for Research, João Ramalho-Santos (Coordinator)

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1. Introduction

1.1. Aims

This document concerns the development and implementation of the TREASURE program (<https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/treasure/>) in the University of Coimbra that aims to *enable* the implementation and adoption of more reproducible, usable and open research principles, practices and outputs, starting at earlier stages of research: master and doctoral studies.

The document includes three main outputs: (i) a list of **reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) practices and outputs** adaptable to different scientific, research and scholarly disciplines and types of studies, (ii) the **assessment criteria** that is being considered to check and assess the implementation of these practices within 2nd (master) and 3rd cycle (doctoral) theses, and (iii) the **procedures** defined to implement and open the opt-in program for enrollment by university master and doctoral candidates.

The aims are threefold: (i) to provide a **range** of RROR activities, practices & outputs that master's and doctoral candidates should be **aware** of and **are encouraged** to include in their research theses, (ii) to **clarify** the criteria used to assess **quality** of the process and output and potentiate **impact**, and (iii) to provide **information** on how to enroll in the program and its associated procedures.

When choosing the practices to implement in their own research, master and doctoral candidates should consider:

- Which practices and outputs **best fit** their research project and each study in particular (e.g., if a thesis has 3 different studies, some practices may apply to some studies and not to others, or the student may want to select different RROR practices for each study)
- Whether any of the following **restrictions** apply to the thesis/dissertation research project and/or any of its studies, limiting student's ability to openly share some of the products (e.g., methods, step-by-step protocols, materials, data):
 - **Sensitive/personal data** (e.g., data protection; informed consent; data sovereignty)
 - **Intellectual property** rights – industrial (including patents, trademark, trade secrets) & copyright
 - **Research security** (e.g., research and innovation misuse and malign influence affecting national security or infringing ethical norms; intelligence data)

Students should consult their supervisors, institutional ethical committees, and other relevant instances to know the national legal and institutional regulations in place and if restrictions apply. When restrictions prohibit sharing of some outputs, students should consider whether they are still able to implement and share other practices and activities, which may include sharing outputs that are not subject to restrictions.

1.2. Explanation of terminologies used (Glossary)

Throughout this guide we use terminologies in their broader meaning as simplifications of more concrete concepts or terms:

- **Discipline:** see Field;
- **Epistemic area:** see Field;
- **Field:** By “field” we mean field of knowledge, discipline, epistemic area, in its broader meaning (such as the broad and second-level areas defined in the Frascati Manual, 2015) or in its more specific meaning concerning specific disciplinary communities within the field. The term “discipline” and “epistemic area” may be used interchangeably;
- **Globally unique identifier:** a compact sequence of characters used to identify an entity (i.e. an identifiable unit of digital or physical type that can be found in a database, registry, repository, ontology, etc), not only locally (within a database or source) but across contexts (source: McMurry et al, 2017). See also Uniform Resource Identifier.
- **License:** Licenses define if and how others can use, modify, and share creative work (source: Konkol, [personal communication](#)). Some licenses are more appropriate for some types of creative work (e.g., Creative Commons licenses are not recommended for computer software or hardware), and should not be applied to works that are no longer under copyright or that are already in the public domain (source: [Creative Commons](#)).
- **Metadata:** all the additional information that provides context and describes the characteristics, properties, and attributes of data, including information that is necessary for understanding and correctly using the raw data within a given context or domain (Cunha-Oliveira et al, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00043.2023>). In the current document, the concept of metadata is extended beyond “data” to include all types of research outputs that are digital objects and require additional information to be properly interpreted either by humans or machines;
- **ORCID:** a free, unique, persistent identifier (PID) for individuals to use as they engage in research, scholarship, and innovation activities. It stands for Open Researcher and Contributor ID (source: [ORCID](#));
- **Output:** by research “output” we refer to the product of one or more research practices (not necessarily included in this document) that has a [Uniform Resource Identifier](#) (URI) and can be accessible in a repository;
- **Persistent identifier (PI or PID):** a long-lasting reference to a document, file, web page, or other object. The term “persistent identifier” is usually used in the context of digital objects that are accessible over the Internet»; «Persistent identifiers are often created within institutionally administered systems, including: Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), the Handle System, Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURLs), Uniform Resource Names (URNs)» among others (source: [Wikipedia](#));

- **Practice:** by research “practice or practices” we refer to a methodology or collection of methodologies used to produce, to report or to disseminate research outputs. Practices can be reproduced or replicated (different sample);
- **Quality:** Quality is an abstract concept that may refer to different things in different disciplines, depending on the goal of assessment. To measure quality, proxy measures are required. In the current program and goals set, quality is defined by the *process* of developing activities, carrying practices and producing outputs in research considering the end goals of openness, reusability, reproducibility and engagement.
- **Research:** we use “research” as an umbrella term of broad meaning to refer to both science (and disciplines using the scientific method), research and scholarship, therefore including fields such as natural sciences, health sciences, social sciences, arts and humanities, technology, engineering and mathematics;
- **RROR:** reusable, reproducible and open research, also reflecting in a broader meaning concepts of transparency, accessibility, inclusivity and engagement;
- **Thesis:** we use “Thesis” to refer both to master *dissertations* and doctoral *theses*; as well as *final activity report* that may be presented in lieu of a thesis for conclusion of master degree in some programs;
- **Uniform Resource Identifier (URI):** An identifier (compact sequence of characters) that is guaranteed to be both uniform and globally unique, identifying an abstract or physical resource (source: The Internet Society, 2005, <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc3986>; McMurry et al., 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414> , Supplementary Information Table 1)
- **Uniform Resource Name (URN):** «A Uniform Resource Name (URN) is a URI that identifies a resource by name in a particular namespace. URNs provide globally-unique names for resources as opposed to providing information about their location (URL)» (source: Mozilla developers); «its scope is to identify resources in a permanent way, even after that resource does not exist anymore. Unlike a URL, a URN doesn't provide any information about locating the resource but simply identifies it, just like a pure URI» (source: [Auth0](#)).

2. TREASURE program: overview of course structure and content

2.1. Procedures

2.1.1. Program structure: Curricular Units

Having the goal of opening of the TREASURE program already in the next academic year, 2025/2026, the program was conceived as two course or curricular units, one for enrollment in the program, and another to check and assess the implementation of the reproducible, reusable and open research (RROR) practices and outputs. A brief description is presented:

Course Units: general typology

- Course units available upon student registration for the 2025-2026 academic year
- Although similar in content, the course units can be selected either as 2nd cycle (Master's) or as 3rd cycle (PhD's) curricular units, as defined by University of Coimbra academic procedures, and respecting the institutional periods and deadlines for selection and registry
- Rectory-level defined, transversal curricular units to the University of Coimbra - can be selected by any master or doctoral course as additional training; can be selected as open option for courses that
- Semestral duration (1st, 2nd)
- Offer extra-ECTS
- B-Learning type (either on site and online)
- Optional - can be taken as additional training or as an open list option (if the study programme allows it)
- Free for the students - for graduate students already enrolled in 2nd and 3rd cycle courses, the units have no additional cost.

Course Unit: Reproducible, reusable and open research I – Introduction to Certification (0.5 ECTS)

Goal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● To enroll in the program (start of program, 1st semester) - This is the first of two curricular units designed to obtain a final certification additional to the degree: formal recognition of the implementation of RROR practices in the research thesis. This unit sets the enrollment in the program and the implementation planning part, providing support & training, whereas the second CU will formally assess implementation of the planned practices.
Curricular year	Any one

Hours	17h (~14h contact time + 3h autonomous work)
Syllabus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Introduction on practices, criteria and program: students create a short list of RROR practices potentially relevant for their project. ○ Training and planning sessions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Students attend "how to" sessions: basic instruction on the RROR practices that they might like to implement; ▪ Students draft an implementation plan (what & how practices will be implemented); ○ Discussion of RROR chosen practices + implementation plan with supervisor ○ Revision & adaptation of implementation plans (using feedback from supervisor) ○ Drop-in sessions: ask questions, get feedback on progress of their implementation plan
Final output and Approval (½)	Final output: Implementation plan (approved by supervisor & degree coordinator).

Course Unit: Reproducible, reusable and open research II - Certification of implementation

Goal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To check implementation (end of program, 2nd semester) - This is the second of two curricular units designed to obtain a final certification additional to the degree: formal recognition of the implementation of reproducible, reusable and open practices in the research thesis. This unit will formally assess the implementation of the practices planned and defined in the first curricular unit.
Curricular year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2nd year (2nd cycle); 2nd-4th years (3rd cycle)
Hours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 30h (~14h contact time + ~16h autonomous work)
Syllabus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Presentation of progress on students' implementation plans: Individual description of modifications made to initial plan + Group discussion on successes & obstacles found during the implementation of the plan.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strategy planning: outline of tasks to fulfill + identification of needed support and/or training; revision of plans/modifications to finalize implementation; completion of outlined tasks ○ Feedback exchange & revision: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Work in small groups: exchange of research products/outputs with students that implemented similar practices, peer-review (by other students); Students incorporate peer feedback. ○ Final Review (by teaching staff): submission of research products/outputs + revision with feedback incorporation ○ Final session: Group discussion - Tips, strategies, lessons learned (success & obstacles found) + suggestions for curricular program improvement
Approval (2/2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Students will receive approval if they successfully implement the defined practices.

Because of the focus on planning and development, besides the initial and final course units, “office open-hours” will be offered to candidates enrolling in the program.

2.1.2. Declaration of Agreement

When enrolling in the program, the students will have to deliver an (I) Implementation Plan and (b) a **Declaration of Agreement** between candidates and supervisors. This declaration, designed to promote and ensure alignment early in the process, will include details on the practices/outputs chosen, what (if any) restrictions apply, conditions for review and update of the implementation plan, and outline expected roles and actions of both students and supervisors. Models considered for the first edition of the TREASURE program are adapted from the Declarations of Agreement for Thesis and PhD students created by the Department of Psychology of the Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich (link: <https://www.lmu.de/psy/en/research/open-science-measures/>).

2.1.3. Program associated events, platforms and procedures:

Annual meeting

The TREASURE program annual event will take place specifically designed to (a) give visibility to good reproducible, reusable, open research practices within and across disciplines and

study types, (b) disseminate the training & implementation program, and (c) provide tangible advice and guidance to program candidates. The annual event is designed as follows:

- Alumni from the program's previous editions will be invited to present what practices and outputs they implemented, challenges faced, and lessons learned (e.g., round table);
- Candidates from the current edition will have the opportunity of presenting the practices implemented (as poster or short talks);
- International speakers from recognized centers where these practices have already been implemented, or that have similar programs, may be invited.

Ambassador program

An ambassador program (alumni group) will be created by year/program edition, with the creation of a community program page (e.g., UC pages, Open Science Framework, OSF) with candidates that completed the course units along with their supervisors and the practices/outputs implemented, to share good practices delivered by the students.

2.1.4. Program Badge and Prize

Badge

Candidates who successfully implement the agreed practices and outputs as stated in the declaration of agreement will receive a **certificate, additional to the degree**, describing the practices and outputs implemented in their thesis, training programs and specific skills earned through course units, therefore attesting their expertise in those particular areas.

Supervisors will also be attributed a certificate.

Prize – RROR champions

Special prizes will be considered in addition to the badge:

- All candidates who are attributed a badge will be invited to participate in a **perspective paper** along with their supervisor, to present what they learn from the program, difficulties and mitigation strategies, sharing also their disciplinary perspective;
- The best RROR implementation (based on quality of the results) will receive an additional prize (to be defined depending on the funding available and partner entities).

2.2. Overview of the Reusable, Reproducible, Open Research Practices & Outputs included in the list

The following RROR enabling practices and outputs were considered for the first edition of the TREASURE program:

1. Author contribution statements *[practice]*
2. Using evidence synthesis techniques to assess the quality of evidence and identify research gaps *[practice]*
3. Preregistration or Study design plans *[output]*
4. Registered Reports *[output]*
5. Preregistered reproducibility or replication studies *[practice]*
6. Open step-by-step methods and protocols *[output]*
7. Stakeholder engagement, Citizen science or Participatory research *[practice]*
8. Open/reusable materials/resources *[output]*
9. Unique and Persistent Identifiers for research materials/resources *[practice]*
10. Open source code and software *[output]*
11. Data sharing *[practice+output]*
12. Following Reporting guidelines *[practice]*
13. Preprints *[output]*
14. Reporting of null results *[output]*
15. Science communication, dissemination, and policy recommendations *[practice]*
16. Open educational materials *[output]*

2.3. Assessment Criteria Framework

The primary **goal** of the TREASURE program is two fold: (i) to raise awareness on concepts of reusability, reproducibility and openness, *enabling* research behaviours that reflect these concepts, and, consequently, (ii) to *support* the implementation of research practices and outputs that abide by these principles, helping the participating students in the identification of relevant practices and outputs for their specific projects and studies and providing support to solve obstacles that may hinder the implementation and improvement of those practices and outputs.

The assessment criteria will reflect this. The program will ensure **quality** of the output by setting criteria that rewards investment in the process development - when performing the activity, following the practice or creating and developing the output, regarding end goals of reusability, reproducibility and openness, depending on the nature of the discipline, and considering the specific practice or output, and if restrictions apply.

For evaluation tools, **peer-review** procedures during the second course unit, and a final **evaluation by a panel** (that may include teaching staff, other UC external members to the program, and members from other institutions) are considered.

Practices and outputs will be assessed based on high-level and practice level criteria, as detailed below.

2.3.1. High-level assessment criteria

These criteria apply to all practices and outputs, irrespective of field, and are required:

- **Visibility within thesis and findability:**
 - **Practices** that can be implemented in a research paper (e.g., author contributions statements, following reporting guidelines, or using globally unique and persistent identifiers) must be **visibly implemented (i.e., reported) in the thesis**.
 - When a **separate output** (e.g., preregistrations, open reusable step-by-step protocols, or open data) is created and shared on a public or restricted access repository, this **output becomes a digital object and must be cited in the thesis**. The citation must allow readers to find the output.
- **Contributor roles:** for all **outputs** resulting from the thesis, an Author contributions statement should specify the contributions of all authors, not just the student. The master or PhD candidate must have an ORCID assigned.
- **Quality assessment:** The practice/output should be assessed based on **quality** regarding achievement of goals of reusability, reproducibility, stakeholders' participation, and openness (RROR), respecting nature of disciplines, and diversity of activities, practices, and outputs. We would prefer that students implement a few practices/outputs with quality standards, instead of implementing many practices/outputs poorly.
- **FAIRness:** When **outputs** are shared on repositories and made available as digital objects, the **FAIR** (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) **principles** apply whenever possible as a proxy for quality of implementation. Essential/required and prioritized indicators will be used based on existing frameworks and/or tools (FAIRsFAIR and RDA frameworks: Devaraju, A., Huber, R., Mokrane, M., Herterich, P., Cepinskas, L., de Vries, J., L'Hours, H., Davidson, J., & Angus White. (2022). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.5). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6461229>; FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>). These **indicators** aim to answer the question of «What needs to be measured to assess the FAIRness of a digital object».

2.3.2. Operationalization criteria

Besides high-level criteria established across practices, assessment criteria are defined at the practice level and may have field or discipline specifications.

For each activity, practice or output, operationalization will clarify how **quality** will be assessed. This may include translation of high-level criteria at the **general practice** level (i.e., what should be generally included in the practice, what does it try to promote/prevent, and if minimum standards to achieve this were reached), or even include **disciplinary or community-based specifications** (e.g., for (meta)data interoperability, what standards are recommended in a particular field and if they were used).

The framework defined for this program is characterized by:

- Definition of minimum standards for Approval (Pass)
- Evaluates process (qualitative approach)
- Evaluates output (qualitative approach, using indicators)
- Considers: complexity of task to perform (“workload”)

Levels:

- Not approved – does not meet minimum standards
- Approved – it meets minimum standards (required* steps) for quality

2.3.3. Criteria to attribute the badge

To receive the TREASURE program course certificate, the following rules need to be verified:

- The candidates need to be registered and successfully complete the **two separate curricular units** (this means course units potentially in the same year/different semesters for master candidates, and in different academic years for doctoral candidates)
- Candidates should select practices and outputs that are meaningful and feasible for their research project, and these should be outlined in the Declaration of Agreement
- Contributors’ statements are required for the thesis, individual studies and different practices
- Implementation of the practices and outputs needs to pass the minimum standards set criteria (“Approval” level)
- Candidates are required to select different practices and outputs, in a number that also considers task workload

- If the same practice or output is implemented in more than one study or chapter of the thesis, all materials for a category will be evaluated collectively and will consider only 1 practice/output.

Table 1. RROR practices and outputs, with examples (when available) by workload level.

TASK DEMAND or WORKLOAD (a priori level)	PRACTICE / OUTPUT	Examples of activities in this task level demand
Required	Author contribution statements	
High	Registered report	
	Preregistered replications	
	Evidence synthesis	
	Open source code	
	Open Hardware	
	Data sharing	
	Open benchmark problems	
	Open educational materials* <i>(depending on time required and complexity)</i>	[TBD]
	Step-by-step methods and protocols* <i>(depending on time required and complexity)</i>	Long protocols
Stakeholder engagement* <i>(depending on time required and complexity, and public engagement)</i>	[TBD]	
Science Communication* <i>(depending on time required and complexity, and public engagement)</i>	Co-creation activity with the public Development of resources with/for the public Full podcast series Ongoing participation in school projects	
Medium	Preregistration	
	Reporting of null results	
	Open educational materials* <i>(depending on time required and complexity)</i>	[TBD]
	Stakeholder engagement* <i>(depending on time required and complexity, and public engagement)</i>	[TBD]

	Science Communication* (depending on time required and complexity, and public engagement)	<i>Practical workshop</i> <i>Letters with Science</i> <i>Article in Frontiers for Young Minds</i> <i>Short podcast series (1–2 episodes)</i> <i>Photo exhibition</i> <i>3MT – Three Minute Thesis</i>
Low	Using Reporting guidelines	
	Unique resource identifiers	
	Preprints	
	Reusable materials/resources* (depending on time required and complexity)	[TBD]
	Step-by-step methods and protocols* (depending on time required and complexity)	<i>Short protocols</i>
	Science Communication* (depending on time required and complexity, and public engagement)	<i>Participation in European Researchers' Night</i> <i>PubhD</i> <i>Pint of Science</i> <i>School visit (one-off sessions)</i> <i>SoapBox Science</i> <i>Science Café</i> <i>Thesis video</i>

TBD: To be defined.

Please note: Specific assessment criteria are detailed at the end of each of the practices and outputs listed in Section 3. These were results of discussions and pre-program exercises to meet minimum standards for technical quality (towards FAIRness) and for scientific, pedagogic or participatory/communication quality. However, the criteria are still under revision and will include further loops of discussion with relevant stakeholders (including those assessing and those being assessed).

3. Reproducible, Reusable And Open Research (RROR) Practices List and Assessment Criteria

To be included in the list, practices should:

- 1) aim to improve the **reproducibility, reusability and openness of research (RROR)**
- 2) be **assessable in a graduate student thesis** (e.g., a peer-reviewed open access research article may not be published before dissertation/thesis finalization)
- 3) be a practice or output **that a graduate student might create** (e.g., Ethics approval is not the student's responsibility)

Note: Some of the practices on the list may already be widely performed in specific fields. We motivate the students and supervisors to go beyond what is already common practice, to take advantage of the current program.

In this section students will find the list of activities, practices and outputs that they are encouraged to implement in their thesis, considering best fit and restrictions that may apply. For each item in the list, a brief definition (what), relevance (why), examples (general, field-specific) and criteria used to assess are outlined.

Please note that the **order of presentation** of the practices and outputs in this document does not necessarily refer to their order of performance within the research or scholar lifecycle – this may change depending on field and research project, and some practices and outputs can be implemented at different time periods.

3.1. Author Contribution Statements

What: Author Contribution Statements are statements that specify the tasks that each author or contributor completed during the research. Author contributions statements can be included in the thesis, in research papers, or in other research outputs that are deposited on repositories (e.g., pre-registrations, study design protocols, data, code). The number and order of authors may differ on different outputs. The author's contribution statement should help readers to understand the reasons for these differences. For example, a researcher who wrote the code for the analysis may be the first author on the repository containing that code but may be a middle author on the paper. Compared to the final paper, a pre-registered study plan may include a smaller number of authors who conceptualized and designed the study.

This statement may follow the CRediT taxonomy (*Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing*), or specify specific contributions without using a taxonomy, as long as it clearly specifies the tasks performed by each author. Some journals specifically require CRediT author contributions statements, whereas others allow authors to determine how author contributions statements are reported.

When: Recommendations point that authors should communicate about authorship expectations and roles at the beginning of a project, when it is less likely to lead to disagreement among the research team members (Holcombe et al, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0244611>), and later update regarding real contributions.

Why:

- Provides a clear public statement of what tasks each researcher performed when completing the study.
- Researchers can receive credit for the different outputs that they created or helped to create during their research, demonstrating their expertise and roles in producing each output, and building an assessable portfolio to showcase different skills.
- Early career researchers can use author contributions statements to show potential employers what they have done.

Examples - What might this look like?

General:
Contributor Roles Taxonomy, CRediT, https://credit.niso.org Other - General approach: Emily Davis devised the project, the main conceptual ideas, proof outline, and wrote the manuscript. Michael Smith worked on all of the technical details and performed the numerical calculations for the suggested experiment. Robert Snow worked out the bound for quantum experiments and verified the results. (source: https://www.cwauthors.com/article/Drafting-Authorship-Contribution-Statement)
Field specific examples:

<p>Architecture:</p> <p>Mohammad Hassan Saleh Tabari: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing—original draft, Visualization. Fereshteh Khojastehmehr: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing—original draft. Günther H. Filz: Conceptualization, Writing—original draft, review & editing. (source: Tabari, M.H.S., Khojastehmehr, F. & Filz, G.H. <i>A-T-G Louvers: a novel geometry and material driven spatial syntax for flexible structures.</i> <i>Archit. Struct. Constr.</i> 5, 32 (2025). https://doi.org/10.1007/s44150-025-00150-6)</p>
<p>Biology:</p> <p>Conceptualization: Caroline Vachias, Emilie Brasset, Vincent Mirouse. Data curation: Yoan Renaud. Formal analysis: Caroline Vachias, Vincent Mirouse. Funding acquisition: Vincent Mirouse. Investigation: Caroline Vachias, Camille Turlonias, Louis Grelée, Parvathy Venugopal, Vincent Mirouse. Methodology: Nathalie Gueguen, Parvathy Venugopal, Graziella Richard, Pierre Pouchin, Emilie Brasset. Project administration: Vincent Mirouse. Software: Pierre Pouchin. Supervision: Caroline Vachias, Emilie Brasset, Vincent Mirouse. Visualization: Yoan Renaud. Writing – original draft: Caroline Vachias, Vincent Mirouse» (source: Vachias C, Turlonias C, Grelée L, Gueguen N, Renaud Y, Venugopal P, et al. (2025) <i>Gap junctions allow transfer of metabolites between germ cells and somatic cells to promote germ cell growth in the Drosophila ovary.</i> <i>PLoS Biol</i> 23(2): e3003045. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3003045)</p>
<p>Mechanical Engineering:</p> <p>Fakhre Alam Khan: Conceptualization; methodology; software resources; validation; formal analysis; resources; original draft; supervision. Zahid Ullah: Conceptualization; software resources; investigation; data curation; review and edit; data visualization; project administration. Muhammad Aashan: Conceptualization; methodology; validation; investigation; data curation; original draft. Farooq Ahmad: Conceptualization; software resources; validation; formal analysis; resources; original draft; data visualization. Muhammad Saad: Methodology; formal analysis; investigation; data curation; original draft. Muhammad Azhar: Methodology; formal analysis; resources; review and edit; data visualization. Every contributor has thoroughly examined and endorsed the finalized manuscript for publication» (source: Khan, F. A., Ullah, Z., Aashan, M., Ahmad, F., Saad, M., & Azhar, M. (2025). <i>Life cycle assessment and energy efficiency of building façade materials: A case study of an educational building in Pakistan.</i> <i>The Journal of Engineering</i>, 2025(1). https://doi.org/10.1049/tje2.70047)</p>

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
NOT APPROVED (does not meet minimum)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statements are not visible in the thesis, but only in resulting works from the thesis; or • Statements are only referred for the whole thesis, not describing different contributor roles (if existing) for the different studies and the different practices and outputs; or

<i>standards for approval)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statements that do not differentiate tasks and roles between authors, or only refer to them in a very general way.
<p>APPROVED</p> <p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author contributions statements need to be visible in the thesis (not in publications resulting from the thesis); • There must be an author contribution statement for the thesis and for all additional outputs (e.g. open step-by-step protocols, open code) resulting from the thesis research work and cited in the thesis. • If the thesis is divided into chapters or papers, each chapter or paper should have a separate author contributions statement (as it refers to different studies). • The statement must describe tasks performed by each individual author. The statement may follow the CRediT taxonomy, or list other specific tasks performed in the research study. Please note: (i) statements such as "the two first authors contributed equally to this work", "all authors approved the final manuscript" or "all authors take responsibility for the work" are not considered author contributions. <p>Recommended: The taxonomy used should describe more than just a few non-specific task categories (e.g. avoid a statement with the following three tasks: designed the study, conducted the study, wrote the manuscript) or if it is detailed regarding other possible roles. In particular, if using CRediT, the statement should use the standard contributions recognized by the CRediT system.</p>

Source and Useful References:

CRediT:

Brand, A., Allen, L., Altman, M., Hlava, M., Scott, J. (2015) Beyond Authorship: attribution, contribution, collaboration, and credit. *Learned Publishing*, 28 (2), 151-155.

<https://doi.org/10.1087/20150211>

Allen, L., Scott, J., Brand, A. et al. Publishing: Credit where credit is due. *Nature* 508, 312–313 (2014).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/508312a>

3.2. Using evidence synthesis techniques to assess the quality of evidence and identify research gaps

What: Researchers may use evidence synthesis techniques, such as systematic reviews, meta-analyses and scoping reviews, to comprehensively identify and assess the quality of the literature on a specific topic and to identify gaps in current knowledge or research that are worth pursuing.

There are several types of evidence synthesis studies.

- **Systematic reviews** use clearly defined procedures to identify all studies that address a specific research question and assess the quality of those studies. When sufficient studies are found, researchers may pool the summary results of these studies to conduct a **meta-analysis** by assessing the size and direction of effects based all identified evidence, rather than drawing conclusions based on individual studies.
- **Individual patient meta-analyses** pool data on individuals from studies that have examined similar research questions to assess the size and direction of effects across studies. Individuals may include patients or participants for clinical studies, or animals for preclinical studies.
- **Scoping reviews** synthesize and map research on a topic, rather than assessing evidence on a narrow research question. Scoping reviews identify the nature, scope and extent of research on a particular topic and often include many different types of studies conducted using a wide range of methodological approaches.

Why:

- Evidence synthesis brings transparency to research questions identification and improvement, turning the identification and definition process more open;
- Rigorously conducted evidence synthesis studies are a valuable tool for identifying knowledge or research gaps (Nyanchoka et al., 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2019.01.005>), decreasing the probability of repeating previous research
- Evidence synthesis studies can reduce waste by helping researchers to avoid design flaws found in previously published studies or preventing researchers from repeating research that has been performed many times before.
- Evidence synthesis studies may be highly cited.
- Early career researchers who conduct rigorous evidence synthesis studies learn to assess the quality of research in their field, which helps them to design better studies. They also strengthen their knowledge of existing evidence addressing their research question.

Examples:

- **Note:** Students should search the existing literature and preregistration platforms for evidence synthesis studies, such as PROSPERO, to confirm that an evidence synthesis study relevant to their research question hasn't already been conducted.
- **Note:** Students are encouraged to seek training in conducting evidence synthesis studies, preregister their study on PROSPERO and use reporting guidelines such as [PRISMA](#) or [MOOSE](#) when designing, conducting and reporting the evidence synthesis study.

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
NOT APPROVED (does not meet minimum)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Relevance (justification) and need (gap in the evidence synthesis previous studies or registries) are not provided; or ● Methodological rigor is lacking (appropriate guidelines for the specific study type - e.g. preclinical; health - and field were not used or followed) <p><i>Please note: Evidence synthesis studies are labor intensive. Unnecessary or poorly conducted evidence synthesis studies waste resources and are therefore discouraged.</i></p>
APPROVED (meets minimum standards for approval)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The evidence synthesis study should include an author contributions statement, specifying the role of the student and other contributors. ● Relevance and need of the evidence synthesis study and need to their thesis research should be established by: (i) searching the existing literature and preregistration platforms for evidence synthesis studies, such as PROSPERO, and confirm that an evidence synthesis study relevant to their research question hasn't already been conducted; (ii) adding a justification for conducting the evidence synthesis study, including insights gained from this search - clearly explain how the evidence synthesis study informed the other research conducted for the thesis (e.g. it may include influencing the selection of research questions, hypotheses tested, or study design and selection of methodological approaches). Note: the justification may appear in other studies included in the paper, rather than in the evidence synthesis study. ● Methodological rigor: Students should follow widely accepted practices for evidence synthesis studies outlined in appropriate guidelines. Specific strategies will depend on the type of study performed.

Additional references & resources:

Nyanchoka, L., Tudur-Smith, C., Thu, V. N., Iversen, V., Tricco, A. C., & Porcher, R. (2019). A scoping review describes methods used to identify, prioritize and display gaps in health research. *Journal of clinical epidemiology*, 109, 99–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2019.01.005>

Moher D, Booth A, Stewart L. How to reduce unnecessary duplication: use PROSPERO. *BJOG*. 2014;121(7):784–786. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-0528.12657>

Page, M. J., Shamseer, L., & Tricco, A. C. (2018). Registration of systematic reviews in PROSPERO: 30,000 records and counting. *Systematic reviews*, 7(1), 32. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-018-0699-4>

3.3. Preregistration

What:

- A pre-registration is a time-stamped study protocol that the researchers deposit on a public repository before starting data collection. For quantitative studies, the pre-registration should include a detailed, complete data analysis plan.
- The protocol can be made public immediately, or it may be made public after an embargo period specified by the researchers (e.g. one year)
- Version control is used to update the study protocol – all modifications have a time stamp and can be explained in the manuscript (e.g., example of a [template](#) to report [Preregistration deviations](#))

Why:

- A pre-registration allows transparent reporting of plans and hypothesis before data collection, and any modifications made to original plan. This enhances trustworthiness in research findings by protecting against [outcome switching](#), [p-hacking](#) and other [questionable research practices](#).
- A pre-registration makes it easier to detect selective reporting (only publishing results that confirm the hypothesis, or are statistically significant) and publication bias by listing all outcomes that you plan to measure
- A pre-registration provides a time stamp proving when you developed the idea and methodological plan
- A pre-registration allows students and supervisors to plan ahead, preventing design flaws

Examples - What might this look like?

Some fields rely on general registries. Other fields use registries that are designed for a particular field or study design.

General registries (across disciplines)		
OSF Registries, https://osf.io/registries - OSF offers different pre-registration templates. If there isn't a template that is more suitable for your study design, try using the AsPredicted template. This is designed to record the most essential pre-registration details.	AsPredicted, https://aspredicted.org/	
Specific study types registries		
Systematic reviews: PROSPERO	Clinical trials: https://clinicaltrials.gov/ , https://clinicaltrials.eu/	

	https://www.isrctn.com/	
Field-specific (discipline-level) registries		
<p>Economics (Pre-analysis plans, PAPs) OSF Registries AEA RCT Registry (https://www.socialscienceregistry.org/)</p>	<p>Psychology OSF Registries Leibniz preregistration platform</p>	

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED (does not meet minimum)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preregistration is not cited or does not have an associated persistent URL at the beginning of the method section (note: OSF links are persistent; private websites/university pages are usually not persistent), • Preregistration is performed after data collection, • There are substantial deviations that have not been made transparent, • Sample size: No power analysis, or incomplete information on assumptions, or no rationale on the extent to which this sample size contributes to an informative study.
<p>APPROVED (meets minimum standards for approval)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pre-registration or study protocol must have an author contributions statement. This statement should show that the student played a prominent role in designing the study and drafting the pre-registration, while also clearly stating the contributions of other authors. • Preregistration is findable, accessible, and public • The pre-registration or study protocol must have a persistent identifier, such as a DOI or handle, and be cited in the thesis / dissertation • Students may either: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deposit a preregistration on a public repository OR ○ Publish a study design protocol in a peer reviewed journal. Study design protocol publications are often used for clinical studies in biomedicine. Students should be aware that the peer review process may delay data collection. ○ Note: A Stage 1 registered report (see next section) may count as a valid preregistration if all criteria for a preregistration are met and the researchers complete the study but decide to publish the study in a different journal instead of proceeding with the Registered Report Stage 2 review. • The preregistration can be embargoed initially, but must be openly accessible on a public repository when the thesis/dissertation is published • For quantitative studies, the preregistration or study design protocol must include a detailed analysis plan and clearly specify planned confirmatory hypothesis tests. This information is critical to distinguish between confirmatory hypothesis tests and unplanned tests, exploratory hypotheses or inductive discoveries tests (https://osf.io/8v2n7_v1).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The preregistration should be time stamped with a date prior to starting data collection (either primary or secondary). If some aspects of data collection have already started, the thesis/dissertation must explain why the pre-registration should still be considered valid <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Note: The data collection start date needs to be stated in the thesis /dissertation • Alignment of preregistration - monography or thesis: there are no deviations; or if there are, they are made transparent and made transparent and justified. • Sample size: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Power analysis is plausible, the assumed effect size is justified (or other good justification). All necessary information is provided (α, β or power, expected effect size, which model was used). Conclusion: The power analysis should be completely reproducible. ○ Or: The extent to which this sample size contributes to an sample size leads to an informative study. • The preregistration or study design protocol must reflect the study that the student performed for their thesis. Minor modifications to study plans are common and can be explained by posting time-stamped modifications to the pre-registration. The pre-registration will not count if the student conducts a very different study from the study that they preregistered (e.g., the student chose to address a different research question or test different hypotheses; the study population changed; the student used different methods from those specified in the preregistration). If the study changes completely, the new study must be preregistered.
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Source and Useful References:

Open Science Initiative - Department of Psychology of LMU (OSF:

<https://osf.io/mgwk8/files/osfstorage>)

Alina Ladyzhensky, Amanda Staller, and Theresa Vo (August 19, 2025). White paper: Preregistration Essentials: Enhancing Transparency in Research. <https://osf.io/cp4x5> ;

Stewart, S. L. K., Rinke, E., McGarrigle, R., Lynott, D., Lunny, C., Lautarescu, A., ... Crook, Z. (2020, October 30). Pre-registration and Registered Reports: a Primer from UKRN.

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8v2n7> ; UKRN Pilots working paper, <https://osf.io/qcgvk>

3.4. Registered Reports

What: A journal reviews a study's introduction and methods before data collection starts, deciding whether to accept the paper based on the quality of the methods, instead of the attractiveness of the results.

In Stage 1, the journal peer reviews the study's planned methods. If the journal decides to issue a provisional acceptance, the researchers to start data collection. In Stage 2, the journal peer reviews the completed paper to confirm that the researchers followed the pre-specified methods, and all modifications were justified; and makes a final decision about acceptance.

Process:

- Authors design the study and submit an incomplete paper containing the introduction and methods to a journal that reviews registered reports.
- Peer reviewers review the introduction and methods before the study is conducted, focusing on the quality of the methods, and may request changes to the study design.
- The journal may provisionally accept the paper before data collection starts. A provisional acceptance means that the journal commits to publishing the results of the study, regardless of whether they confirm the hypothesis, if the authors follow the methods outlined in the registered report.
- The researchers perform the study, as specified in the registered report, and write the paper
- The journal reviews the completed paper once the study is completed, to confirm that the research team followed the methods specified in the registered report and any protocol deviations are justified.
- If accepted, the paper is published.

Why:

- Authors obtain reviewer feedback to correct study design and methodological flaws before starting the study. Students learn how to design robust studies.
- The decision to publish the study is based on the quality of the design, not whether the results are surprising or interesting.
- Students can obtain provisional acceptance, confirming that their paper will be published before they start the study.
- By prespecifying the study plan, registered reports aim to avoid questionable research practices such as p-Hacking, HARKing or publication bias.
- Registered reports enhance the trustworthiness of research, which benefits researchers and non-academic stakeholders (e.g., industry can rely on more rigorous methods & findings when choosing objects for investment)

Cautionary note: When publishing a registered report, you can't start data collection until your protocol has been peer reviewed. This can be time-consuming and delay your research. One solution to this problem is to submit to Peer Communities In – [Registered Reports](#). This

organization is designed to review registered reports. They allow you to schedule your submission date in advance, and they will book reviewers who commit to reviewing your registered report within 2 weeks. [Peer Communities In – Registered Reports](#) partners with various journals, who commit to offering provisional acceptances if reviewers from Peer Communities In – Registered Reports decide that your registered report should be accepted. See the Peer Communities In – Registered Reports list of partner [journals](#).

Examples - What might this look like:

General information: Several journals now accept Registered Reports. You can find a list of participating journals from different fields on the following websites:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OSF resource: https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports (Participating journals) Study resource (in OSF study repository): list of journals accepting RR and corresponding policies: https://osf.io/4sfwv Examples of RR studies linked in the RR Peer Community In (PCI) repository: https://rr.peercommunityin.org/ Stewart, S. L. K., Rinke, E., McGarrigle, R., Lynott, D., Lunny, C., Lautarescu, A., ... Crook, Z. (2020, October 30). Pre-registration and Registered Reports: a Primer from UKRN. https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8v2n7 		
Field-specific examples of Journals:		
Biology BMC Biology	Chemistry PeerJ Chemistry journals	Economics Journal of Development Economics; Oxford Open Economics
Neuroscience Cortex	Psychology Nature Human Behaviour	Sport Sciences Science & Medicine in Football journal

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
NOT APPROVED (does not meet minimum)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Registered Report Stage 1 or Stage 2 submission is not accepted. Study stops at Registered Report Stage 1 acceptance <p><i>Please note: If study stops at Registered Report Stage 1 acceptance, the practice will be considered under Preregistration.</i></p>
APPROVED (meets minimum standards for approval)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Registered Report Stage 2 acceptance The article must include an author contributions statement, that clearly specifies the roles or contributions of the student and all other authors. The student must have a finalized stage 1 and stage 2 registered report, accepted by the journal. Students can either provide an acceptance letter from the journal, or the DOI for the publication. These documents must clearly note that the article is a registered report. <p><i>Please note: If the student has a stage 1 RR, but hasn't completed stage 2, this will be counted as a preregistration if the stage1 report is openly accessible on a</i></p>

	<i>public repository. Students are encouraged to pre-register their study on a public repository before they start data collection.</i>
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Source and Useful References:

Center for Open Science (n.d.). Registered Reports: Peer review before results are known to align scientific values and practices. Retrieved July 1, 2025, from <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports>

Additional references & resources:

Stewart, S. L. K., Rinke, E., McGarrigle, R., Lynott, D., Lunny, C., Lautarescu, A., ... Crook, Z. (2020, October 30). Pre-registration and Registered Reports: a Primer from UKRN. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8v2n7>

3.5. Preregistered reproducibility or replication or studies

What: Researchers attempt to confirm the results of previously published studies by repeating a previously published study (replication study) or using data and, if available, code from a previous study to determine whether they can reproduce the results (reproducibility study).

Why:

- Studies from psychology, biomedicine, and other fields have demonstrated that findings from many studies are not reproducible or replicable. Knowing which findings do, and don't, replicate, and under what conditions, is essential for researchers, policy-makers and other decision makers in many fields.
- Conducting a reproducibility or replication study helps early career researchers to identify problems that make it difficult to reproduce or replicate results. Researchers learn how to avoid these problems by improving the conduct and reporting of their own studies to improve reproducibility and replicability.
- Reproducibility and replication studies can provide important information about why studies aren't reproducible or don't replicate, which can lead to new insights and research directions.

Examples – what may this look like:

Field-specific examples:	
<p>Psychology List of replication studies in Psychology: https://osf.io/ezcu/</p>	<p>Biology - Health sciences Reproducibility Project: Cancer Biology, https://www.cos.io/rpcb Neves, K., Carneiro, C. F., Wasilewska-Sampaio, A. P., Abreu, M., Valério-Gomes, B., Tan, P. B., & Amaral, O. B. (2020). Two years into the Brazilian Reproducibility Initiative: reflections on conducting a large-scale replication of Brazilian biomedical science. <i>Memorias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz</i>, 115, e200328. https://doi.org/10.1590/0074-02760200328</p>

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED (does not meet minimum)</p>	
<p>APPROVED</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author contributions statement: The reproducibility or replication study should include an author contributions statement, specifying the role of the student and other contributors.

<p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Justification: In the thesis, students should clearly justify why they chose a particular study, or part of a study, to replicate or reproduce. They should also how closely the reproduction or replication followed the original study methodology, justifying any deviations. • Preregistration: The reproducibility or replication study must be preregistered, so that the protocol for conducting the study is clearly specified before data collection begins. This includes specifying the definition for successful reproducibility or replication. Students can get credit for their preregistration under the preregistration criteria and the preregistration should meet all criteria outlined in that section. • Methodological rigor: Students should follow accepted practices for reproducibility and replication studies. Specific strategies will depend on the type of study performed.
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Source and Useful References:

Block, J., & Kuckertz, A. (2018). Seven principles of effective replication studies: strengthening the evidence base of management research. *Management Review Quarterly*, 68(4), 355-359. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11301-018-0149-3>

Jekel, M., Fiedler, S., Allstadt Torras, R., Mischkowski, D., Dorrough, A. R., & Glöckner, A. (2020). How to Teach Open Science Principles in the Undergraduate Curriculum—The Hagen Cumulative Science Project. *Psychology Learning & Teaching*, 19(1), 91-106. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1475725719868149>

3.6. Open reusable step-by-step methods and protocols

What: Authors openly share or publish step-by-step protocols or detailed methods, describing how to perform a specific procedure. This allows others to reuse, adapt and modify the method to answer new research questions. Examples include posting a reusable step-by-step protocol on a public repository, publishing a reusable step-by-step protocol in a protocol's journal, or publishing a methods paper describing and validating a new method.

Reusable step-by-step protocols offer detailed descriptions of the steps that researchers follow to implement a specific method. Step-by-step protocols should be very detailed, allowing researchers to implement the method successfully. Private protocols contained within electronic lab notebooks may be sufficiently detailed to allow others to implement the method but would need to be openly shared in a repository.

Please note: Study design protocols, which provide a detailed written plan for a specific study, are considered under Preregistration and Registered Reports.

Why:

- Methods are one of the most useful and reusable outputs that researchers create.
- Reproducibility starts with methods. We can't reproduce a study if we don't know what was done.
- Detailed methods are essential for responsible reuse of shared data. We can't reuse data responsibly without knowing how the data were generated.
- Sharing step-by-step protocols by publishing them or depositing them on a public repository allows others to reuse methods to replicate results or to answer new research questions.
- Researchers get credit for methods development work when others reuse and cite their methods.
- Well documented protocols make it easier to train new members of the research team and ensure that everyone is following the same procedures. They can also capture undocumented knowledge, which can be especially important in research groups with high turnover.
- Writing detailed study design protocols or reusable step-by-step protocols forces the researcher/student to organize, clarify and refine the elements of the study, enhancing scientific rigor and efficacy (Hulley, et al., 2013). Researchers also develop skills for documenting and clearly communicating complex procedures.
- Researchers who are seeking jobs in industry or academia can document their experience developing or implementing certain methods, creating a portfolio for future employers

Examples - What might this look like?

General / Multidisciplinary:		
<p>PLoS ONE and protocols.io, https://www.protocols.io/</p>	<p>Visual experiments protocols: JoVE, https://www.jove.com/</p>	<p>MethodsX, https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/methodsx</p>
<p>Workflow Hub (a registry for describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows - it aims to facilitate discovery and re-use of workflows in an accessible and interoperable way. This is achieved through extensive use of open standards and tools, including CWL, RO-Crate, Bioschemas and GA4GH's TRS API, in accordance with the FAIR principles. WorkflowHub supports workflows of any type in its native repository), https://workflowhub.eu/</p>	<p>Lab notebooks (if accessible in a repository openly or through a restricted access protocol), examples:</p> <p>Open lab notebooks, https://openlabnotebooks.org/about/</p>	
Field-specific examples:		
<p>Computational science</p> <p>Workflows, https://aiida-tutorials.readthedocs.io/en/latest/</p>	<p>Law</p> <p>Article defining relevant sources of legal information and search strategies, https://www.boompportaal.nl/tijdschrift/ReM/lawandmethod-D-15-00005</p>	<p>Natural Sciences</p> <p>protocols exchange: An open repository (preprint server) of community-contributed protocols sponsored by Nature Portfolio, welcoming protocols from all areas of the natural sciences: https://protocolexchange.researchsquare.com/</p>
<p>Psychology + Health Sciences</p> <p>Journal: Trials, https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript/study-protocol + https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript/study-protocol/structured-study-protocol-template</p> <p>Journal: Clinical Trials, https://journals.sagepub.com/home/ctj</p>	<p>Sport Sciences</p> <p>BMC Sports Science, Medicine and Rehabilitation, https://bmcsportsscimedrehabil.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript/study-protocol</p>	

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED</p> <p><i>(does not meet minimum)</i></p>	
<p>APPROVED</p> <p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author contributions: The protocol or method output must include an author contributions statement that clearly specifies the role of the student and other contributors in developing and/or documenting the method or protocol. • Protocols or methods outputs may include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A reusable step-by-step protocol, describing how to perform a specific procedure, that is <i>posted on a public protocol repository</i> ○ A reusable step-by-step protocol, describing how to perform a specific procedure, that is <i>published in a protocol journal</i> ○ A <i>methods paper</i> describing how to perform a new method and validating that method, that is published in a methods journal or a journal that publishes methods articles • Relevance: The protocol or method must be used in the thesis. • Citation of protocol or method output: The protocol or method output must have a persistent identifier, such as a DOI, and should be cited in the appropriate location in the methods section. The citation should allow readers to find the output. • Detail: The protocol or methods paper should be sufficiently detailed to allow others to implement, reuse or adapt the method for reuse in another context. • Recency: In some fields, protocols and methods quickly become outdated. The time stamp on the protocol or method output should be within two years of starting data collection for the study. If the protocol or methods output is more than 2 years old, the student may: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Deposit and cite an updated version of the protocol, reflecting methods used during their research, in a repository. ○ If modifications to the protocol or method were very minor, students can describe these modifications in the methods section of their thesis, after citing the protocol or method output. ○ If there were no modifications to the protocol or methods, students can clearly state in the thesis that they followed the cited protocol without modifications.

3.7. Stakeholder engagement & Citizen Science

What: Citizen science or Stakeholder engagement are umbrella terms for methods that engage stakeholders in the research process (e.g., citizens, patients, industry, policymakers and regulators, etc.) as co-researchers or co-scientists. Participation can occur during any stage of the research lifecycle (e.g., development of research questions, definition of methods, data collection, data curation, etc) and may involve different approaches, from more contributory (e.g. collection and analysis of samples), to collaborative, towards more co-creative (i.e., wider participation from ideation to interpretation ([Bonney et al. 2009](#))).

‘Citizen science’ usually focuses on the involvement of society at large, whereas ‘Stakeholder engagement’ is the preferred term to describe the involvement of specific groups or communities (patients, industry, policymakers, regulators, etc).

Also known as: Participatory research; Community or Public engagement; Engaged Research Approach

Why:

- It increases the likelihood that the research will meet stakeholders’ needs, involving them in the knowledge production process (e.g. biomedicine: it brings patients associations to show students the perspective of patient’s lives)
- [Research is undertaken in collaboration with the communities who are most likely affected by the research outcomes](#)
- Given it aims to solve needs, it may attract funding directed to solve needs and priorities.
- Students develop skills in communication, collaboration, and project management by interacting with diverse stakeholders
- Stakeholders’ engagement as co-scientists contributes to scientific literacy of society

Examples - What might this look like?

Researchers may engage with patients, companies and employees to understand their needs, or involve communities in the co-production of research questions, methods, and materials. Researchers may also engage citizens or stakeholders in specific activities, such as using platforms with games for cell identification, asking people to transcribe documents, assign keywords and attribute classifications, or send photos with geolocation for mapping purposes. Researchers may use methods such as ethnographic research.

You can find General information and projects:		
European Citizen Science Platform, https://eu-citizen.science/	Portuguese Citizen Science platform,	Citizen science projects, https://www.zooniverse.org/projects

	https://www.cienciadada.pt/	
Some field-specific examples:		
<p>Anthropology (‘Ethnographic research’) Ethnographic research with <u>visual media</u></p>	<p>Arts & Humanities <u>Museology: engaging audience and visitors in museum governance and activities</u></p>	<p>Ecology and biodiversity Citizen Science e.g., https://invasoras.pt/</p>
<p>Economics & Business</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consultation with companies and policy makers; • Business analysis and consultation with stakeholders to understand their needs 	<p>Health: Preclinical research <u>Lalu, et al. 2024: Protocol for co-producing a framework and integrated resource platform for engaging patients in laboratory-based research.</u></p>	<p>Health Research</p> <p>Three first layers of the “onion” model [annex 2]: Welcome Trust (2011). Community Engagement – Under the Microscope. Retrieved July, 1, 2025, from https://media.tghn.org/articles/community_engagement_under_the_microscope.pdf</p>
<p>History</p> <p>Creation of keywords and alternative descriptions, https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/juliehgibb/stereovision</p> <p>Historical research in Luxembourg, https://historesch.lu/en/contribute/</p>		<p>Physics, Astronomy and Space Sciences</p> <p>Solar Stormwatch CME catalogue – space weather citizen science project, https://doi.org/10.1002/2014SW001119</p>

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED</p> <p>(does not meet minimum)</p>	
<p>APPROVED</p> <p>(meets minimum)</p>	<p>[Note: The criteria are to be defined considering discussions within the core team and relevant stakeholders: University of Coimbra citizen science hub; Portuguese national meeting of citizen science. We aim to consider: quality - context, significance, process and outcomes, but also to assess impact - the effects of</p>

standards for approval)	projects on the participants themselves and on society at large. The SCOPE Framework (Himanen et al., 2021) will be used as tool in this reflection exercise]
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Additional References & Resources:

UKRN Primer - Community Engagement in Research (Last edited: February 17, 2024),

https://osf.io/preprints/osf/8jgxt_v1

Community engagement and involvement | NIHR, <https://www.nihr.ac.uk/research-funding/global-health/community-engagement-and-involvement>

Participatory Monitoring and Evaluation – Participatory Methods

Schaefer, T., Kieslinger, B., Brandt, M., van den Bogaert, V. (2021). Evaluation in Citizen Science: The Art of Tracing a Moving Target. In: Vohland, K., et al. The Science of Citizen Science. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_25

Nash, C. (2015). Evaluating Community-Based Participatory Research. Guelph, ON: Community Engaged Scholarship Institute. <https://atrium.lib.uoguelph.ca/xmlui/handle/10214/8902>

Phillips, T. B., Ferguson, M., Minarchek, M., Porticella, N., and Bonney, R. 2014 User's Guide for Evaluating Learning Outcomes in Citizen Science. Ithaca, NY: Cornell Lab of Ornithology. Available on 6th May from https://participatorysciences.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/USERS-GUIDE_linked.pdf

Bonney, R., Ballard, H., Jordan, R., McCallie, E., Phillips, T., Shirk, J., Wilderman, C. (2009). Public Participation in Scientific Research: Defining the Field and Assessing Its Potential for Informal Science Education. Washington, D.C.: Center for Advancement of Informal Science Education (CAISE). Available on 5th May 2025 from: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED519688>

Joint Research Centre: Institute for Environment and Sustainability, Guimarães Pereira, Â., Nascimento, S. and Ghezzi, A., From citizen science to do it yourself science – An annotated account of an on-going movement, Publications Office, 2014, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2788/12246>

Association for Advancing Participatory Sciences, <https://participatorysciences.org/resources/research-evaluation/>

[onion model] Welcome Trust (2011). Community Engagement – Under the Microscope. Retrieved July, 1, 2025, from https://media.tghn.org/articles/community_engagement_under_the_microscope.pdf

3.8. Open/reusable resources/materials

What: Resources or materials that are used to conduct research and are shared in a repository, allowing other researchers to access and reuse the materials. Examples of resources and materials might include reagents, model organisms, educational materials, psychological tests, experimental tasks, tools, samples or curated documents. Resources and materials may be shared in an open repository, a restricted access repository with clearly specified procedures for accessing the materials (e.g., biobank; collection), or a commercial repository, depending on the type of material. Resources should have unique persistent identifiers (see practice below) to help others to determine exactly what resource was used.

Why:

- Sharing resources/materials allows others to reuse newly created resources/materials, increasing efficiency and accelerating discovery.
- Open materials save time and resources
- Researchers get credit for resource creation when others reuse and cite the resource
- Researchers who are seeking jobs in industry or academia that involve the creation of materials can document their experience, creating a portfolio for future employers.

Examples - How this may look like:

General examples:		
General Research Resource Identification Portal, https://rrid.site/		
Field-specific examples:		
Arts & Humanities Museology: practical resources created from the collaborative research including toolkits (physical and digital), written guides, and online exhibitions (source UKRN Art & Design)	Anthropology Field notes, Sanjek, R. (Ed.) (1990). Fieldnotes: The makings of anthropology. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, https://archive.org/details/fieldnotes-making0000unse ; https://anthropod.net/2013/08/14/a-template-for-writing-fieldnotes/	
Chemistry (Pharmaceutical Chemistry) Database of commercial-available compounds, https://zinc15.dockin g.org/	Psychology Open stimuli sets (OASIS, https://www.benedekkurdi.com/#!portfolio/project-4.html), Open experiments (https://pavlovia.org/), or Psychological test instruments available in REPOPSI,	Health Sciences / Biology / Anthropology Samples and materials deposited in a biobank or repository (students do the deposit, filling the required files and detailing the metadata required to deposit): Original dataset (raw

ChemSpider: Search and Share Chemistry - Homepage	https://osf.io/5zb8p/ ; Open Test Arxiv, https://www.testarchiv.eu/	data) of the mass spectrometry proteomic studies can be deposited on the Open Access Repository PRIDE with a dataset identifier
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Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED</p> <p><i>(does not meet minimum)</i></p>	
<p>APPROVED</p> <p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Author contributions: The role of the student and other contributors in creating the material should be documented in the repository, if possible. If the repository does not provide information on who created or contributed the resource or material, this should be documented in an author contributions statement within the student’s thesis. ● Availability: Resources or materials should be available in a materials repository. Depending on the type of material, this could be an open, restricted access repository or commercial repository. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open repositories are used for resources that are easily maintained, such as files containing educational materials, image libraries or experimental tasks. ○ Restricted access repositories are often used for sensitive materials, such as materials that are associated with patient data. Users who request access may have to adhere to specific conditions to access the materials. Restricted access repositories must have a clearly defined procedure that allows users to request data and specifies conditions for gaining access. Procedures might specify who potential users should contact to request access, what forms must be completed, who reviews submitted requests, and the criteria for obtaining permission to reuse the resource or materials. ○ Commercial repositories are permitted for resource intensive materials that must be maintained and/or continuously produced, such as model organisms, antibodies, cells lines, and plasmids. These repositories maintain and sell materials shared by investigators to researchers who would like to reuse the materials. ○ Note: Privately shared resources and materials that are only accessible by contacting the researcher or are not in a repository that allows researchers from other institutions to access stored resources and materials, are not permitted.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Citation: The resource or material should have a unique persistent identifier, if one can be obtained for this resource type, and should be cited in the thesis. The citation should allow readers to locate the resource.• Metadata: The resource or material should be accompanied by detailed documentation describing the resource and its creation, to help others to use the resource responsibly.• Relevance: The resource or material must be created as part of the student's thesis.
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3.9. Unique identifiers for research materials and resources

What: Unique and persistent identifiers are ID numbers or codes assigned to research material to help researchers identify exactly what was used (like DOIs, but for research materials). Ideally this should be both globally and persistent identifiers. Examples include Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) for cell lines, antibodies, model organisms, plasmids, software and tools and core labs, or CAS numbers for chemicals.

What is not: Details like *catalog numbers, product numbers, version numbers, supplier names or equipment make and model information are not unique persistent identifiers*, as they are only identifiable *locally* (within a database or source). These details change over time as suppliers update their product portfolio and websites. Research studies have shown that many materials described in published papers cannot be identified from this information alone; hence, research communities have started developing unique persistent identifiers to create catalogs of lasting identification numbers for particular types of materials and resources.

Why:

- Using unique persistent identifiers to specify exactly what was used improves transparency of research methods and increases reproducibility of methods and results
- Investigators always know what was used, even if the catalog number or supplier website changes, the supplier offers other new products that are similar, or the product is discontinued or sold to another supplier
- Some unique persistent identifier systems offer warnings about problematic materials. For example, the Research Resource Identifier (RRID) database gives warnings about cell lines that are known to be contaminated or misdiagnosed. Researchers can check materials for warnings before starting their study.
- **Added benefits for researchers who create resources:** Some unique persistent identifier systems, like RRIDs, allow researchers to create new persistent identifiers for resources that they create, “claim” these resources and add them to their ORCID profile. ORCIDs are unique persistent identifiers for researchers. Researchers who create new resources should include unique persistent identifiers in instructions on how to cite the resource. Having a unique persistent identifier makes it easier to cite a resource and quantify the impact of your work.

Examples – What might this look like?

Researchers should report unique persistent identifiers for items that have them in their manuscripts. Adding unique persistent identifiers to supply ordering lists for the research team makes it easy for everyone to order the right supplies and report correct identifiers in their manuscripts.

General:	
RRID (cell lines, antibodies, plasmids, model organisms like mice and rats, software and tools, core labs), https://www.rrids.org/	
Field-specific examples:	
<p style="text-align: center;">Life Sciences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical substances collection: CAS Registry, https://www.cas.org/cas-data/cas-registry • Proteins: UniProt, https://www.uniprot.org/ • The Identifiers.org Resolution Service provides consistent access to life science data (e.g. genes, parasites lifecycles, etc.) using Compact Identifiers (provides an assigned unique prefix and a local provider designated accession number (prefix:accession)), https://identifiers.org 	<p style="text-align: center;">Arts and Humanities</p> <p>Digital objects national registry (PT) (Registo Nacional de Objetos Digitais – RNOD), providing a persistent link, RNOD - Registo Nacional de Objectos Digitais</p>

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
NOT APPROVED (does not meet minimum)	
APPROVED (meets minimum standards for approval)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic criteria: the student used unique persistent identifiers to describe materials and resources used • More demanding: Unique identifiers are specified for all materials that require them

Additional references & resources:

McMurry JA, Juty N, Blomberg N, Burdett T, Conlin T, Conte N, et al. (2017) Identifiers for the 21st century: How to design, provision, and reuse persistent identifiers to maximize utility and impact of life science data. PLoS Biol 15(6): e2001414. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414>

Plomp, E. (2020). Going Digital: Persistent Identifiers for Research Samples, Resources and Instruments. Data Science Journal, 19(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-046>

Bandrowski A, Brush M, Grethe JS et al. The Resource Identification Initiative: A cultural shift in publishing [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. F1000Research 2015, 4:134 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.6555.2>)

FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, EOSC Executive Board, Hellström, M., Heughebaert, A., Kotarski, R. et al., A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

3.10. Open source code / Open software

What: Open-source software and code refers to sharing of software and code on a public repository with licenses that allow others to reuse, adapt and distribute the software or code; or to publish an open access software paper.

Why:

- Making code openly available allows others to implement computational methods, reproduce findings, or reuse code and software for new projects.
- Developing and making available open source code and software allows students to develop programming, debugging, documentation and collaborative skills, which are valuable skills in the job market. Students who share code and software document their experience, creating a portfolio that they can share with future employers.
- Researchers get credit for software and code development when others reuse and cite their code or software

Examples – What might this look like?

There are several general resources for sharing software and code:		
The R project for statistical computing, https://www.r-project.org ; researchers create and share packages, allowing others to perform particular types of analyses	GitHub, https://github.com/	Journal for Open software papers, https://joss.theoj.org/
Jupyter Notebooks, jupyter.org		
Field-specific examples:		
<p>Anthropology</p> <p><i>Ethnographic qualitative</i> data statistical software – RQDA, https://rqda.r-forge.r-project.org</p> <p><i>Forensic anthropology:</i> 'JSDNE': A novel R package for estimating age quantitatively with the auricular surface by Dirichlet normal energy, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2024.106080 + https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/JSDNE/index.html</p>	<p>Computational materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computational materials: Open code and software, https://www.materialscloud.org/work/menu Virtual machine, https://quantum-mobile.readthedocs.io/en/latest/ 	<p>Economics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computational Economic models, https://github.com/OpenSourceEconomics • Quantitative economic modelling, https://github.com/QuantEcon • Reproducible workflows, https://lachlandeer.github.io/snakemake-econ-r-tutorial/ • Leibniz Information Centre for Economics - Open code in Economics and business studies, https://openeconomics.zbw.eu/en/knowledgebase/open-code-in-economics-and-business-studies/?cat=172
<p>Law</p> <p>Legal Text Mining resources, https://github.com/Liquid-</p>	<p>Neuroscience</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fMRIprep, Reproducible workflows for preprocessing of 	<p>Psychology</p> <p>Open-source software for cognitive and behavioral experiments,</p>

Legal-Institute/Legal-Text-Analytics ; https://liquid-legal-institute.com/workinggroups/legal-text-analytics/	data, https://fmriprep.org/en/stable/	PsychoPy, https://www.psychopy.org/ ; LabsJS, https://lab.js.org/
Social Sciences NetLogo Models, https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/models/	Engineering OpenFOAM (from complex fluid flows involving chemical reactions, turbulence and heat transfer, to acoustics, solid mechanics and electromagnetics), https://www.openfoam.com/documentation/overview	Social and Behavioral Sciences Implicit Association Test (Harvard), -programming language (JS): https://minnojs.github.io/docs/start/-study-materials (pictures, etc): https://www.projectimplicit.net/resources/study-materials/
Computer science Platform to save data and models - https://www.openml.org/	Healthcare Models: open source simulation tools; https://youtu.be/nytslQOjumI?feature=shared	Physics, Astronomy and Space Science Open source models, https://centaur.reading.ac.uk/100589/3/OpenResearchCaseStudy-2021-Barnard.pdf
Environment, Agriculture, Decision science TAMSAT-ALERT, https://centaur.reading.ac.uk/86472/1/OpenResearchCaseStudy-2019-Black.pdf ; https://github.com/tamsat-alert/v1-0		

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
NOT APPROVED (does not meet minimum standards for approval)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Script not available or • script is only partly available; or • script is poorly annotated/commented; or • script does not run without errors; or • script is not properly cited*; or • script does not have a license that allows reuse <p><i>*This means it lacks: proper credit attribution (author contribution statements); an unique identifier (URL) that is machine actionable; globally unique, interoperable, and recognized by domain experts; persistence of URL and metadata (e.g. deposited in Zenodo); accessibility to software and associated metadata; and lack of documentation to outline, e.g., specification of software version and other software dependencies.</i></p>
APPROVED (meets minimum)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Script(s) available, with persistent URL. <i>Please note: Zenodo, OSF links, or institutional open repositories are persistent; GitHub or private websites/university pages usually are not;</i> • Script(s) is(are) properly cited; AND

<i>standards for approval)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Essential documentation* is provided; AND • Proper license for reuse (e.g., GPL, MIT, Apache); AND • Script it is referred to in the appropriate part of Methods section, AND/OR, • Script runs through without errors (if applicable), AND/OR • Use of comments to explain the code; AND/OR • The individual code sections are sections are related to the core parts of the work (e.g: 'Hypothesis 1"); AND/OR • Use of containers (e.g. Docker), AND/OR • Use of dummy datasets (if applicable -- i.e. if the scripts require data that cannot be shared) <p><i>*Documentation means: An outline of the contents of the repository; Installation and/or run-through instruction; Dependencies (e.g. software versions and properly cited third party software). Documentation may be in any format, preferably smth non proprietary, e.g. a txt, md, or html document. Some software platforms, e.g. Python or R, have dedicated markdown editors / file formats that make this easy and neat, and which can be explicitly recommended (e.g. Jupiter notebooks).</i></p> <p>Please note:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider differences between source code (e.g. analysis) and software (e.g., experimental tasks), from Chue Hong et al. (2019) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Code: textual representation of a program or module following the syntactic constraints of a programming language ○ Software: a program, module, library, package, dependency, code, script or framework, i.e. software encompasses all of the above. • Restricted access needs to be an option (with procedures for access described in metadata) for software that may raise ethical concerns if openly shared (e.g., psychological experimental tasks may have emotional effects on participants or general public, and there might be ethical concerns on sharing of this software).
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Source and Useful References:

Open Science Initiative - Department of Psychology of LMU (OSF:

<https://osf.io/mgwk8/files/osfstorage>)

Smith AM, Katz DS, Niemeyer KE, FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. 2016. Software citation principles. PeerJ Computer Science 2:e86 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.86>

Chue Hong, N. P., Allen, A., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., de Waard, A., Smith, A. M., Robinson, C., Jones, C., Bouquin, D., Katz, D. S., Kennedy, D., Ryder, G., Hausman, J., Hwang, L., Jones, M. B., Harrison, M., Crosas, M., Wu, M., Löwe, P., Haines, R., ... Pollard, T. (2019). Software Citation Checklist for Authors (0.9.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3479199>

University of Cambridge: Research Data Management – Research Data: How to choose a Licence for Open Source code or software. Retrieved on May, 7, 2025, from <https://www.data.cam.ac.uk/data-management-guide/choosing-software-licence>

Additional resources & references:

Turner, A., Topor, M., Stewart, A. J., Owen, N., Kenny, A. R., Jones, A. L., & Ellis, D. A. (2020, October 30). Open Code and Software: a Primer from UKRN. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/qw9ck>

Garijo D, Ménager H, Hwang L, Trisovic A, Hucka M, Morrell T, Allen A, Task Force on Best Practices for Software Registries, SciCodes Consortium. 2022. Nine best practices for research software registries and repositories. PeerJ Computer Science 8:e1023 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1023>

Free Software Foundation, Advice on how to choose a license, Available 7th May from <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/license-recommendations.html>

Open Source Initiative, Available 7th May from <https://opensource.org/>

European Commission, Joinup Licensing Assistant, <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/eupl/solution/licensing-assistant/find-and-compare-software-licenses>

3.11. Data sharing (FAIR; Open)

What: Research data are shared in a repository, ideally in a way that makes them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Depending on the type of data, data may be shared on an open repository or a restricted access repository. For responsible and proper data reuse either by humans or machines, documentation and contextualization (known as *metadata*) should always be provided with data. Metadata may include information such as study description, methods used, data types, licensing, access and reuse conditions.

Openness and FAIRness (FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) of data mean different things and relate to different practices. Data can be open while not being FAIR, and data can be FAIR while not being openly accessible. In the current program, given reusability and reproducibility goals, we encourage first towards FAIR data and metadata and, whenever possible, openly available data.

- **Open data sharing:** Data that is not sensitive may be shared in an open access repository. Open data must be accompanied by detailed metadata, which provide information about what the dataset is and how the data were collected. High quality metadata is essential for responsible data reuse.
- **Restricted access data sharing:** Sensitive data may be shared on a restricted access repository, where potential users need to apply or agree to adhere to certain conditions to access the data (either by humans or machines). Archiving data on a restricted access repository ensures that a clean, reusable version of the dataset is stored in a findable location with a long-term preservation strategy. Procedures for accessing restricted access data should be clearly specified (e.g. who to contact, what forms or paperwork should be completed to access the data, conditions for reuse). Data shared on restricted access repositories should include high quality metadata to facilitate responsible data reuse. Two particular cases highlight options for data reuse without (full) data sharing, in case of sensitive data or other restrictions apply:
 - **Data visitation:** «application of mining algorithms and other querying methods without necessitating access to the original data sets» (Basajja et al., 2022, In Leonelli, 2025)
 - **Synthetic data:** «Synthetic datasets mimic real datasets by preserving their statistical properties and the relationships between variables. Importantly, this method also reduces disclosure risk to essentially nil as no record in the synthetic dataset represents a real individual.» (Quintana, 2021)
- **Metadata sharing:** When data cannot be shared on an open access or restricted access repository, researchers may still share open metadata describing contextual information about the dataset and methods used to collect the data. This helps others to find the dataset and initiate collaborations.

Cautionary note: Data sharing requires sound data management to ensure data quality. Researchers who are interested in sharing data should create a data management plan when designing the study, to address considerations such as ethical requirements, use of standards for (meta)data, documentation, storage, access and security of data.

Why:

- Sharing of data and connected properly described metadata allows others to reproduce findings, reuse data for evidence synthesis or to answer new research questions. Access to metadata allows others to find relevant studies and datasets, even when the data is not fully open.
- Students learn robust data management and curation skills, including metadata standards and data sharing protocols, which are increasingly valuable in academia and non-academic environments
- Both academic and external stakeholders can access large, high-quality datasets to inform their R&D activities, accelerating discovery and potentiating research-based innovation
- Researchers get credit for data generation when others reuse and cite their data

Examples – Where can I share data?

General repositories for data sharing:		
Zenodo, https://zenodo.org/ ; Dryad, https://datadryad.org/ ; Figshare, https://figshare.com/ ; OECD, https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets.html ; OSF (research data deposited within project folders), https://osf.io/ ;	PT government: https://dados.gov.pt/pt/datasets/	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure (or EUDAT CDI) is an infrastructures of integrated data services and resources supporting research in Europe, https://eudat.eu/
Institutional repositories 'open/FAIR (meta)data' for data sharing:		
Dataverse research data repositories, check institutional repositories at https://dataverse.org	Open access: DataShare (UnivEdinburgh), https://datashare.ed.ac.uk/ ; MADA (Univ Mannheim), https://madata.bib.uni-mannheim.de/	Restricted access: DataVault (Univ Edinburgh), https://digitalresearchservices.ed.ac.uk/resources/data-vault ; Data Cube (Univ Mannheim), https://www.bib.uni-mannheim.de/en/teaching-and-research/research-data-center-fdz/services-of-the-fdz/sharing-data-in-a-secure-environment/
CERN, https://opendata.cern.ch/		
Field-specific repositories 'open/FAIR (meta)data' where to find datasets:		
Health and Social care DataLoch (Univ Edinburgh), https://dataloch.org/	Neuroscience OpenNeuro, https://openneuro.org/ , NeuroVault, https://neurovault.org/	Social sciences Qualitative data, https://qdr.syr.edu/

YODA, restricted access repository for sharing clinical data, https://yoda.yale.edu/		
Pharmacology, Pharmaceuticals Briggs, et al. (2021). Guidelines for FAIR sharing of preclinical safety and off-target pharmacology data. ALTEX, 38(2), 187–197. https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.2011181	Physics CERN, https://opendata.cern.ch/	
Psychology, Medicine Release of synthetic data (using synthpop.R package), https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.53275 Major-Smith D, Kwong ASF, Timpson NJ et al. Releasing synthetic data from the Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC): Guidelines and applied examples [version 2; peer review: 3 approved, 1 approved with reservations]. Wellcome Open Res 2024, 9:57 (https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.20530.2)	Humanities Journal of Open Humanities Data, https://openhumanitiesdata.metajnl.com/ Classical studies – Ancient Greek, Homeric Epic: e.g., Page Images of primary and secondary sources; Primary source texts; Translations; Machine-readable dictionaries, Rich linguistic annotation (https://hdsr.mitpress.mit.edu/pub/m0dqvamt#nfftokcs9j3 - Categories of data available for Homeric Epic)	Law data collection may consider people, countries, but also texts inspection and interpretation (https://guides.ll.georgetown.edu/c.php?g=365532&p=7886015 ; https://libguides.vermontlaw.edu/EmpiricalLegal/data ; https://hls.harvard.edu/library/research-services/legal-databases/)
Economics Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, Open Economics Guide - open data, https://openeconomics.zbw.eu/en/knowledgebase/open-data-in-economics-and-business-studies/?cat=90		

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
NOT APPROVED <i>(does not meet minimum standards for approval)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper credit attribution (author contribution statements) is not available; • (meta)Data is not available through a persistent unique identifier (PID); • poor metadata (does not identify nor cites standards used for metadata and/or data); • does not allow reuse or access through restricted protocol; • Without a license (that allows reuse or that establishes in which conditions (meta)data can be accessed) • (meta)data is not deposited in a trusted repository
APPROVED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An Author Contribution Statement should describe all authors and roles of those involved in the creation of the output • Dataset available, with persistent unique identifier;

<i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of a trustworthy repository as defined e.g., by Cannon et al. (2021) or OpenAIRE; • Rich metadata - identifies and cites the standards, database, etc, used for organizing data and metadata; clear about or links to methods underlying its acquisition/creation; clear on how to access and how to reuse; AND/OR • Attributed license (CC0 or CC BY) - data is available with license for reuse OR procedures for accessing restricted access data should be clearly specified in metadata (e.g. who to contact, what forms or paperwork should be completed to access the data, conditions for reuse) • A data accessibility statement should be included in the thesis, ideally in the appropriate sections (e.g. Results). Procedures for accessing restricted access data should be clearly specified in metadata (e.g. who to contact, what forms or paperwork should be completed to access the data, conditions for reuse) • A data management plan must be presented, detailing the plan developed during thesis work to address considerations such as ethical requirements, use of standards for (meta)data, documentation, storage, access and security of data • Human research data sharing needs to abide to the ethical and legal requirements: appropriate use of informed consent, anonymization, rights management, and access control (https://osf.io/preprints/osf/wp4zu_v1)
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Source and Useful References:

Open Science Initiative - Department of Psychology of LMU (OSF:

<https://osf.io/mgwk8/files/osfstorage>)

OpenAIRE (n.d.). How to find a trustworthy repository for your data. Retrieved June, 25, 2025, from <https://www.openaire.eu/find-trustworthy-data-repository> : "OpenAIRE recommends to use the Creative Commons CC0 waiver or the CC-BY licence for open access to data."

Cannon, M., Graf, C., McNeice, K., Chan, W. M., Callaghan, S., Carnevale, I., Cranston, I., Edmunds, S. C., Everitt, N., Ganley, E., Hrynaszkiewicz, I., Khodiyar, V. K., Leary, A., Lemberger, T., MacCallum, C. J., Murray, H., Sharples, K., Soares E Silva, M., Wright, G., ... (Moderator) Sansone, S.-A. (2021). Repository Features to Help Researchers: An invitation to a dialogue. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4683794>

Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. Martone M. (ed.) San Diego CA: FORCE11; 2014 <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egy>

Additional references & resources:

Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, Article 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Rocca-Serra, P., Gu, W., Ioannidis, V. et al. The FAIR Cookbook - the essential resource for and by FAIR doers. *Sci Data* 10, 292 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02166-3> Daniel S Quintana

(2020) A synthetic dataset primer for the biobehavioural sciences to promote reproducibility and hypothesis generation eLife 9:e53275. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.53275>

Publications Office of the European Union, Data.europa.eu data quality guidelines, Publications Office of the European Union, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2830/333095>

Basajja, M., Suchanek, M., Tadele Taye, G., Yohannes Amare, S., Nambobi, M., Folorunso, S., Plug, R., Oladipo, F., & van Reisen, M. (2022). Proof of concept and horizons on deployment of FAIR data points in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Data Intelligence*, 4(4), 917–937. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00179

Borgman, C. L., & Groth, P. (2025). From Data Creator to Data Reuser: Distance Matters. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.35d32cfc>

Crane, G., Babeu, A., & Tauber, J. (2025). Humanities Data Reuse: Humanity First. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.598a17b4>

3.12. Follow Reporting Guidelines

What: Study design and reporting guidelines are recommended, consensus-based, community accepted standards that specify essential details that authors should report for specific types of studies to ensure transparency, robustness and reproducibility. Reporting guidelines may include checklists, flow diagrams, or structured text to guide authors in reporting necessary elements. Guidelines are generally designed for specific study designs or research methods.

Reporting guidelines are very common in biomedical sciences and psychology but may be less common in other fields.

Why:

- Facilitates accurate, complete, and transparent reporting of research studies to improve research reproducibility and usefulness.
- Students gain skills in good research practices, by using standard recommendations to guide study design and reporting
- Many journals require authors to adhere to reporting guidelines. Ensuring that you collect all necessary information when designing your study reduces the likelihood that your paper will be rejected for missing information. Using a reporting guideline to write your paper reduces the likelihood that reviewers or editors will return your paper due to missing information, or that you will need to add additional details during revision or initial manuscript checks.

Cautionary note: Researchers should also look for study design guidelines for their study type. Study design guidelines help authors to address critical considerations when designing their study. Examples include the PREPARE guideline for preclinical animal research and the SPIRIT guideline for clinical trials.

Examples - How this may look like:

General examples:	
Sex and Gender in Research (SAGER Guidelines), Heidari et al. Sex and Gender Equity in Research: rationale for the SAGER guidelines and recommended use. Res Integr Peer Rev 1, 2 (2016). https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-016-0007-6	
Reporting Checklist for patient & public engagement: Staniszewska, S., Brett, J., Simeria, I., Seers, K., Mockford, C., Goodlad, S. et al. (2017). GRIPP2 reporting checklists: tools to improve reporting of patient and public involvement in research. BMJ 358:j3453. doi:10.1136/bmj.j3453	Systematic reviews meta-analysis, PRISMA, https://www.prisma-statement.org/
Field-specific examples:	
<p style="text-align: center;">Health Sciences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equator network (collection of guidelines – check for guidelines for your study design type), https://www.equator-network.org/ 	<p style="text-align: center;">Neurosciences</p> <p>COBIDAS, https://www.equator-network.org/reporting-guidelines-keyword/cobidas/ ;</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Epidemiology: STrengthening the Reporting of OBservational studies in Epidemiology (STROBE), https://www.strobe-statement.org/ ● Clinical trials: CONSORT for randomized controlled trials, TREND for non-randomized trials; COMET, standardized sets of outcomes (“Core Outcome Sets”, COS) ● Animal pre-clinical studies, ARRIVE, https://arriveguidelines.org/ ● Smith AJ, Clutton RE, Lilley E, Hansen KEA, Brattelid T. PREPARE: guidelines for planning animal research and testing. <i>Laboratory Animals</i>. 2017;52(2):135-141. doi:10.1177/0023677217724823 	<p>cred-nf: https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32176800/;</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Psychology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SPIRIT, https://www.goodreports.org/reporting-checklists/spirit/, 	

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED</p> <p><i>(does not meet minimum)</i></p>	
<p>APPROVED</p> <p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Appropriateness and citation: In their thesis, the student mentions and cites at least one reporting guideline that is relevant to the type of study that they performed. Reporting guidelines are typically mentioned and cited in the methods section. The statement should specify the stages of the study during which the reporting guideline was used, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ “This systematic review was designed, conducted and reported in accordance with the PRISMA guideline.” ○ “This manuscript was written in accordance with the ARRIVE guidelines.” ○ “This study was designed in accordance with the SPIRIT guidelines and conducted and reported in accordance with the CONSORT guidelines.” ○ “This study was conducted and reported in accordance with the STROBE guidelines. The SAGER guidelines were used to report details related to sex and gender.” ● Reporting completeness: Details required by the guideline are reported in the thesis. If a requested item is not relevant, the student should explain why. If a requested item was not done, this should be clearly stated. ● Checklist: If the guideline has a checklist specifying the location in the paper where each item is reported, with or without text reporting each item, this checklist is included in the thesis.

Source and Useful References:

UK EQUATOR Centre (n.d.). EQUATOR network: Enhancing the QUALity and Transparency Of health Research. Retrieved on July 1, 2025, from <https://www.equator-network.org/>

3.13. Preprints

What: Preprints refer to research papers that are posted on an open public server prior to peer review. Authors can post updated versions as they improve and refine the paper.

Why:

- Authors can get feedback and improve the paper before it is published. Preprints can be shared with a wider audience than the small number of reviewers who examine the paper during journal peer review.
- Papers that are first posted as preprints start accumulating citations sooner, as others have already seen and started citing preprints by the time that they are published. The preprint website typically provides a link to the published version once the paper is published in a peer reviewed journal.
- Funders increasingly allow authors to list preprints in funding applications. This is particularly valuable for early-stage researchers and others who want to show evidence of their work. Preprints can be posted within a few days, whereas peer review and publication are time consuming and may not be completed in time for a grant application deadline.
- Authors get scooping protection, as the time-stamped preprint clearly shows when the research team first posted their paper.
- Students can make their studies and outputs visible earlier, allowing for networking opportunities, and providing early career recognition.

Examples – Where can I post preprints?

General examples and where to find preprint repositories:	
Reviews and Other types of papers: https://osf.io/preprints	All types of studies: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_preprint_repositories
Field specific preprint repositories:	
Anthropology Preprints may be referred to as working paper series, https://anthropology.utk.edu/opportunities/working-paper-series/	Physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical engineering and systems science, and economics ArXiv, https://arxiv.org/ (original preprint repository)
Biology and life sciences bioRxiv (original research only), https://www.biorxiv.org/ Case study: Quantitative Biology > Genomics, a preprint that is not published in a journal but it is vital to the genomics field, https://arxiv.org/abs/1303.3997	Chemistry ChemRxiv, https://chemrxiv.org/engage/chemrxiv/public-dashboard
Information Science e-prints in Library and Information science, http://eprints.rclis.org/	Law Bepress Legal Repository – offers working papers and preprints, https://law.bepress.com/

Medicine	Psychology
MedRxiv (original research only; Preprints are preliminary reports of work that have not been certified by peer review. They should not be relied on to guide clinical practice or health-related behavior and should not be reported in news media as established information), https://www.medrxiv.org/	PsyArXiv, https://osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv
Social Sciences	Sports sciences
socArXiv, https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv	SportRxiv, https://sportrxiv.org/index.php/server
Economics	
SSRN, https://www.ssrn.com/index.cfm/en/ern/ RePEC, http://repec.org/	

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
NOT APPROVED <i>(does not meet minimum standards for approval)</i>	
APPROVED <i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Author contributions: The preprint contains an author contributions statement, specifying the role of the student and all other contributors who conducted the research. • Citation: The preprint has a DOI or another persistent identifier and is cited in the student’s thesis. For example, the paper in the thesis might include a statement such as “This paper has been posted as a preprint (citation).” • A study or paper from the student’s thesis is posted on a public preprint repository, before publication in a peer reviewed journal.

Additional references & resources:

Spitschan, M., Rumsey, S., Jaquier, M., & Galizzi, M. M. (2020, October 30). Preprints: a Primer from UKRN. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m4zyh>

3.14. Reporting of null results

What: Researchers report studies and results that don't support their hypotheses, i.e., report of (true) negative or null findings, following the analytical test of a hypothesis. When reporting studies with mixed (i.e., both positive and negative) results, researchers report all results obtained during a study, including those that aren't statistically significant or don't support their hypotheses.

While the practices on this list focus on the report at the thesis level, students are also strongly encouraged to publish null results to avoid selective reporting and publication bias in the research literature.

Why:

- Research projects should result in the potential for the transfer of the new knowledge, allowing other researchers to reproduce the results (as part of their own research or for evaluation purposes). This includes research activities that have negative results (e.g., an initial hypothesis fails to be confirmed or a product cannot be developed as originally intended). If one aims to produce new knowledge, the results cannot remain tacit (i.e. remain solely in the minds of the researchers), as they, and the associated knowledge, would be at risk of being lost (OECD, 2015, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>).
 - Reporting of null results reduces biases in the research literature and avoids the questionable research practices of selective reporting, publication bias and HARKing.
 - **Selective reporting:** Researchers only report the data or outcome variables that supported their hypothesis or were statistically significant in their research paper and omit other outcome variables that did not support their hypothesis or were not statistically significant.
 - **Publication bias (towards positive results):** Researchers don't publish or report studies that have negative or null results or don't support the researchers' hypothesis. To prevent positive publication bias, which leads to inaccurate effect sizes, both (true) positive and (true) negative findings need to be reported. This will provide an accurate representation of the research field, rather than focusing merely on surprising or novel findings (Schweinfurth et al, 2024).
 - **HARKing (“Hypothesizing After Results are Known”):** In confirmatory studies, researchers present a *post hoc* hypothesis (i.e., one that is actually based on or informed by one's results) as if it were an *a priori* (i.e., before testing and knowing results) hypotheses (Kerr, 1998, https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327957pspr0203_4), reframing their hypotheses to create a more compelling narrative. This often includes emphasizing statistically significant, interesting or surprising findings, and omitting null findings.
- Selective reporting, publication bias and HARKing distort the evidence base that researchers, policy makers and others use to plan future studies and make decisions.

Relying on a biased and distorted evidence base can increase research waste and lead to flawed decisions that harm the intended beneficiaries of research.

- Reporting of null results reduces research waste, as others are less likely to attempt similar studies.

Examples:

- The Missing Pieces: A Collection of Negative, Null and Inconclusive Results, <https://collections.plos.org/collection/missing-pieces/>
- Hornig M, Brieese T, Buie T, Bauman ML, Lauwers G, Siemetzki U, et al. (2008) Lack of Association between Measles Virus Vaccine and Autism with Enteropathy: A Case-Control Study. PLoS ONE 3(9): e3140. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0003140>

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED</p> <p><i>(does not meet minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	
<p>APPROVED</p> <p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preregistration: The study must be preregistered. The preregistration must clearly define the research question, objectives and hypotheses, and identify all outcome variables that will be assessed during the study and specify all planned analyses. Otherwise, readers cannot determine whether all outcome variables are reported in the study results. Students can get credit for their preregistration under the preregistration criterion if the preregistration meets all criteria outlined in the preregistration section. ● Null results should be qualified statistically, this can be in a Frequentist or Bayesian framework, e.g. with equivalence tests, Bayesian estimation, or Bayes factors ● The significance threshold (or similar Bayesian equivalent) should be made clear in the paper ● Missing results: Sometimes variables that researchers planned to measure are not measured due to changes in the study plan, equipment failure, feasibility problems, limited resources, or other issues. Any outcome variables that could not be measured or analyzed should be reported in the thesis, along with a justification explaining why the variable wasn't measured, analyzed or reported. ● Complete reporting of null results:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The research question, objectives and hypothesis tested in the paper should match those presented in the preregistration, confirming that there was no HARKing. ○ The thesis should fully report all outcome variables defined in the preregistration, with justifications provided for variables that could not be measured, analyzed or reported. Statistical analyses should match those outlined in the preregistration, to confirm that researchers have not used p-hacking («a compound of strategies targeted at rendering non-significant hypothesis testing results significant»; Stefan, & Schönbrodt, 2023, pp.1). ○ Complete data for null results should be presented in the study or supplemental files of the thesis. Statements such as “data not shown” should not be used. ○ If hypothesis testing is performed, authors should clearly state that results above the threshold for statistical significance are not statistically significant. Researchers should not use hedges about p-values that are slightly above the threshold (e.g., trending towards significance, approaching statistical significance). ○ The results section of the paper should include a statement such as “All studies and outcome variables that were measured, as defined in the preregistration, have been reported.” This statement can be adapted according to the study type and circumstances. ○ Null results should be interpreted consistently and clearly — i.e., if the significance threshold is $p < 0.05$, a p value of 0.051 should be interpreted as not significant rather than "marginally significant" or similar ○ The abstract should present a balanced view of the study’s findings. Students should not spin the abstract, by highlighting positive results while failing to mention null results.
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Source and Useful References:

Stefan AM, Schönbrodt FD.2023 Big little lies: a compendium and simulation of p-hacking strategies. R. Soc. OpenSci. 10: 220346. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.220346>

Additional References & Resources:

Bik E. M. (2024). Publishing negative results is good for science. Access microbiology, 6(4), 000792. <https://doi.org/10.1099/acmi.0.000792>

Clark, A. (2017). Negative results: A crucial piece of the scientific puzzle. EveryONE. <https://everyone.plos.org/2017/10/26/negative-results-a-crucial-piece-of-the-scientific-puzzle/>

OECD (2015), Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>

Mlinarić, A., Horvat, M., & Šupak Smolčić, V. (2017). Dealing with the positive publication bias: Why you should really publish your negative results. *Biochemia medica*, 27(3), 030201.

<https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2017.030201>

Schweinfurth, M. K., & Frommen, J. G. (2024). Beyond the null: Recognizing and reporting true negative findings. *iScience*, 28(1), 111676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.111676>

3.15. Science communication & Policy recommendations

What:

- Science communication is an umbrella term covering a wide variety of activities, including professional communication by scientists; interactions between scientists and members of the public; the media representation of science; and the ways people use scientific knowledge in their own lives (Mellor & Webster, 2017, p.1).
- Researchers, science communicators and journalists share materials, activities or results of research projects with different publics in plain language. They may offer concise or more comprehensive analyses, along with recommendations to inform policymakers, academics, practitioners, or the public.
- Defined as organized, explicit, and intended actions that aim to communicate scientific knowledge, methodology, processes, or practices in settings where non-scientists are a recognized part of the audience (Horst, Davies, & Irwin (2017, p.884)).
- Currently, it employs the Public participation paradigm (leaving behind the simple Dissemination paradigm), aiming an open dialogue and deliberation between the public, experts and decision makers (Kappel K and Holmen SJ, 2019).

Also known as: Science dissemination and Outreach, Knowledge exchange with stakeholders; Public engagement (although different from Stakeholder Engagement)

Why:

- General public and non-academic stakeholders have facilitated access to the knowledge produced by the use of plain language and adequate dissemination methods for the target public
- Science communication improves scientific/research literacy and allows the public to interact and benefit from research, facilitating translation of research results to policies
- It potentiates the relevance of the research
- It facilitates recruitment of research participants
- Improving the design of the research to address ethical concerns, improving the research tools and make it easier for the people taking part
- Making it more likely that the findings of the research will be used to make a difference to service users' lives.
- Students gain skills in writing, abstracting and translating research jargon, pitch and communication. These skills may be highly valuable in the job market.
- Students who are seeking jobs in industry, education or academia that involve science communication can document their experience, creating a portfolio for future employers

Examples - What might this look like?

Science communication may take many formats and be targeted for different audiences. Different activities involve different levels of public engagement and require different levels of time commitment. It can refer to competitions to pitch your research in simple language and very short time; talks and round tables for broader audiences; informal talks at public spaces (e.g., bar), production of materials to be disseminated in social media (e.g., newspapers, etc) or through dedicated pages and websites; or get more formal structures and purposes such as policy briefs and laws summarized into simpler language.

General examples:	
Competitions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FameLab, https://www.cheltenhamfestivals.org/our-projects/famelab/famelab-international , • 3MT (3-minute thesis competition), https://threeminutethesis.uq.edu.au/ • ScienceSlam, https://www.scienceslam.de/ • Falling Walls Lab (innovative ideas), https://falling-walls.com/lab 	Informal talks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PubhD • Pint of Science • Soapbox Science
Lay Summaries (texts using plain language for non-specialist audiences): https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/how-guides/write-lay-summary	Digital objects and resources: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Games • Graphical abstracts • Infographics
Recommendations for policy makers and other relevant stakeholders (e.g. industry): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • policy briefs • participation in industry fairs, round tables, and the like. 	
Media and social media, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Podcasts • issuing media releases; • giving media interviews; • participating in media debates. 	Participation in big and general events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Researchers' Night • Science Fairs and Festivals • Participation in exhibitions, and speed dating • Theatre plays • Visits to schools and other institutions • Science clubs organization
Field-specific examples:	
<p style="text-align: center;">Arts & Humanities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural heritage, Europeana, https://www.europeana.eu/en , https://humanitiesdata.com/resources/284 • Museology: interactive websites including images of objects, diagrams, and descriptions of research processes (source: UKRN Art & Design); 	<p style="text-align: center;">Chemistry</p> Chemistry World, https://www.chemistryworld.com

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Museums: https://journal.sciencemuseum.ac.uk/article/the-research-museum-a-place-of-integrated-knowledge-production/#abstract 	
<p style="text-align: center;">Health Sciences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EuroHuntington, https://eurohuntington.org/news/ • Clinical trials: Cochrane Dissemination Checklist, https://training.cochrane.org/online-learning/knowledge-translation/how-share-cochrane-evidence/dissemination-essentials-checklist 	<p style="text-align: center;">Neuroscience</p> <p>Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian Museum, https://gulbenkian.pt/cerebro-mais-vasto-que-o-ceu/</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Physics</p> <p>Youtube channel MinutePhysics, https://www.youtube.com/@MinutePhysics</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Law</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UCL; Faculty of Laws, Policy Briefs, https://www.ucl.ac.uk/laws/research/making-impact/shaping-world-through-impactful-research/policy-briefs • World Justice Project, https://worldjusticeproject.org/our-work/publications/policy-briefs

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED</p> <p><i>(does not meet minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	
<p>APPROVED</p> <p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An Author contribution statement should be included. • The activity or materials should have a description, included in the thesis/dissertation (in case it was planned as a project task) or as attached as Appendix to the thesis (in case there was no previous plan) • The description should follow a report form, incorporating the initial plan (e.g., using a predefined CANVA tool) for the activity/material - idea and methods/content should be suitable with regard to the target audience, feedback from the audience (e.g. questionnaire), and a self-evaluation analysis by the student (e.g. SWOT analysis). • If created and digitally available as resources of the activity, a link or citation to the materials/activity should be provided

Source and Useful References:

- FRN awards in Outstanding Promotion of Science to the Public, <https://www.fnr.lu/fnr-awards-new/> (link to [guidelines](#))
- Duke, M. (2012). 'How to Write a Lay Summary'. DCC How-to Guides. Edinburgh: Digital Curation Centre. Available online: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/how-guides>

3.16 Open Educational resources

What: Open educational resources are digital or printed teaching, learning, and research materials that are in the public domain or have been released under an open license that allows no-cost access, use adaptation, redistribution by others with limited or no restrictions (<https://guides.library.harvard.edu/OER>).

Why:

- Making educational resources openly available reduces barriers in access to education and educational materials.
- Instructors can reuse and adapt these materials for teaching in other settings.
- Researchers who share open educational materials may expand their networks, develop collaborations, and build their professional reputation among students and instructors when others reuse these materials.
- Researchers who are seeking jobs in education, higher education or academia can document their experience, creating a portfolio for future employers

Examples – What might this look like?

General examples:	
Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training (FORRT), https://forrt.org/	OSSCAR (Open Software Services for Classrooms and Research), https://www.osscar.org/
Research Integrity: Embassy of Good Science, https://embassy.science/wiki/Main_Page	Repository of national educational videos, from the digital services (FCCN) of the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (several fields): https://educast.fccn.pt/?locale=pt
Open Nordic library-produced LEARNING RESOURCES that develop students' academic digital competence (in Danish only): https://learninglib.org/	Openly Available Sources Integrated Search (OASIS), https://oasis.geneseo.edu/
OER commons, https://oercommons.org/	
Field-specific examples:	
<p>Neuroscience</p> <p>Simply neuroscience, https://www.simplyneuroscience.org/</p>	<p>Economics</p> <p>Leibniz Information Centre on Economics - Open Educational Resources in Business studies and economics, https://openeconomics.zbw.eu/en/knowledgebase/open-educational-resources-in-business-studies-and-economics/?cat=147</p>
<p>Life Sciences</p> <p>Computational resources in the life sciences: ELIXIR, TeSS, https://tess.elixir-europe.org/</p>	

Criteria to assess the practice:

Assessment levels	Description of level
<p>NOT APPROVED</p> <p><i>(does not meet minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	
<p>APPROVED</p> <p><i>(meets minimum standards for approval)</i></p>	<p>Materials will be assessed both according to technical and pedagogical quality.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical quality - we consider the recommendations by Garcia et al. (2020) on how to turn training materials FAIR to promote reusability: materials and resources should have been shared, have a persistent unique identifier (e.g. DOI, handle), be properly described (with metadata required to enable their (re)use - open or limited via an access-request mechanism with clear access rules -, and detailing learning outcomes and prerequisites), be made available for (re)use by their authors, with proper licensing and/or without copyright restrictions, using interoperable formats that allow (re)use with different software programmes and operating systems. • Pedagogical quality: context and significance, how appropriate for the intended audience/target public <p><i>Recommended: For enhanced findability and discoverability, training materials should be shared on repositories or online registries that target the intended specific audience(s). It is also recommended to keep materials up-to-date and allow contributions from others (make materials contribution friendly by specifying rules for participation and contribution).</i></p>

Source and Useful References:

Garcia L, Batut B, Burke ML, Kuzak M, Psomopoulos F, Arcila R, et al. (2020) Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. PLoS Comput Biol 16(5): e1007854.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007854>

Wiegers, L., & van Gelder, C. W. G. (2019). Illustration for "Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR" (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593258>

5. Practices That Were Considered But Were Not Included In The Current List

In this section we list the practices and outputs that were considered, but that were not included due to (a) lack of available training support resources in the University of Coimbra, (b) not fulfilling criteria to be included in the list.

5.1. Practices and Outputs Lacking Currently Available Training Support

- Open source hardware
- Open benchmark problems
- Scholarly edition
- Positionality statements (or researcher reflexivity)
- Ontological and epistemological assumptions

5.2. Practices Not Fulfilling Criteria To Be Included In The List

- Thesis proposals project [*must meet the criteria for Preregistration*]
- Research data management plan (DMP) [*will be used as path towards Data sharing*]
- Open Access
- Open Innovation
- Open Repositories
- Open to Other Knowledge Systems
- Policy research agendas

6. References

The following framework was used for guiding principles:

Himanen, L., Conte, E., Gauffriau, M., Strøm, T., Wolf, B., & Gadd, E. (2024). The SCOPE framework - implementing ideals of responsible research assessment. *F1000Research*, 12, 1241. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.140810.2>